

**MATEMATIK MODELLASHTIRISH YORDAMIDA CHIZIQLI
ALGEBRAIK TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASINI KRAMER VA TESKARI
MATRITSA USULLARIDA YECHISH**

Asrorova Charos Baxtiyor qizi.

“TIQXMMI” Milliy Tadqiqot universitetining
Qarshi Irrigatsiya va Agrotexnologiyalar instituti assistenti

asrorovacharos10@gmail.com

Muxtorova Shohida Negmat qizi.

Toshkent Kimyo- Texnologiya
Instituti Shahrisabz filiali assistenti

muxtorovashohida1998@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada matematik modellashtirish yordamida chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar sistemalarini Kramer va teskari matritsa usullari yordamida yechish jarayoni ko'rib chiqiladi. Tenglamalar sistemasini yechishda ushbu usullarning afzalliklari va kamchiliklari tahlil qilinadi. Kramer qoidasidan foydalanib yechim topish va teskari matritsa usuli yordamida yechimlarni izlash jarayonlari to'liq bayon etiladi. Maqola amaliy muammolarga misollar keltirib, usullarni qo'llash uchun mos, sodda va aniq yo'llarni taqdim etadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Matematik modellashtirish, chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar, tenglamalar sisteması, Kramer qoidasi, teskari matritsa usuli, determinant, noma'lumlar, kengaytirilgan matritsa.

Annotation: This article examines the process of solving systems of linear algebraic equations using mathematical modeling by employing Kramer's rule and the Inverse matrix method. The advantages and disadvantages of these methods in solving systems of equations will be analyzed. The process of finding solutions using Kramer's rule and searching for solutions through the Inverse matrix method

will be thoroughly explained. The article provides practical examples of problems, presenting accessible, straightforward, and clear approaches for applying the methods.

Keywords: Linear equations, algebraic systems, mathematical modeling, Cramer's method, Inverse matrix method, solutions, coefficients, determinants, solving systems, numerical computing.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматривается процесс решения систем линейных алгебраических уравнений с использованием математического моделирования, применяя правило Крамера и метод Обратная матрица. Будут проанализированы преимущества и недостатки этих методов при решении систем уравнений. Порядок нахождения решений с использованием правила Крамера и поиск решений с помощью метода Обратная матрица будет подробно изложен. Статья предоставляет практические примеры задач, предлагая доступные, простые и четкие подходы для применения методов.

Ключевые слова: Линейные уравнения, алгебраические системы, математическое моделирование, метод Крамера, метод Обратная матрица, решения, коэффициенты, определители, решение систем, численные вычисления.

Chiziqli algebraik tenglamalar tizimlari ko'plab amaliy muammolarni yechishda muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu maqolada Kramer qoidasi va teskari matritsalar usuli yordamida chiziqli tenglamalar sistemalarini qanday yechish mumkinligini ko'rsatamiz.

Chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini Kramer usuli bilan yechish. Chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasining yechimini topishni oldin ikki noma'lumli ikkita chiziqli tenglamalar sistemi uchun qaraymiz. Ushbu ikki noma'lumli ikkita chiziqli tenglamalar sistemi

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x + a_{12}y = b_1 \\ a_{21}x + a_{22}y = b_2 \end{cases}$$

dan, birinchi tenglamani a_{22} ga, ikkinchi tenglamani $-a_{12}$ ga hadma-had ko'paytiramiz va hosil bo'lgan tenglamalarni qo'shamiz, natijada

$$(a_{11}a_{22} - a_{21}a_{12})x = b_1a_{22} - b_2a_{12} \quad (1)$$

tenglama hosil bo'ladi. Huddi shunga o'xshash, 1-tenglamani $-a_{21}$ ga, 2-tenglamani a_{11} ga hadma-had ko'paytirib, hosil bo'lgan tenglamalarni qo'shib ushbu fodalarni hosil qilamiz:

$$(a_{11}a_{22} - a_{21}a_{12})y = b_2a_{11} - b_1a_{21} \quad (2)$$

$$(a_{11}a_{22} - a_{21}a_{12}) = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}, \quad b_1a_{22} - b_2a_{12} = \begin{vmatrix} b_1 & a_{12} \\ b_2 & a_{22} \end{vmatrix},$$

$$b_2a_{11} - b_1a_{21} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & b_1 \\ a_{21} & b_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

bo'lgani uchun, quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritib

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Delta_1 = \begin{vmatrix} b_1 & a_{12} \\ b_2 & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}, \quad \Delta_2 = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & b_1 \\ a_{21} & b_2 \end{vmatrix}$$

va (2) tengliklarni

$$\Delta \cdot x = \Delta_1, \quad \Delta \cdot y = \Delta_2$$

ko'rinishda yozish mumkin. Bundan $\Delta \neq 0$ bo'lsa,

$$x = \frac{\Delta_1}{\Delta}, \quad y = \frac{\Delta_2}{\Delta}$$

bo'ladi, yoki determinantlar orqali yozsak:

$$x = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} b_1 & a_{12} \\ b_2 & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}}, \quad y = \frac{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & b_1 \\ a_{21} & b_2 \end{vmatrix}}{\begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} \end{vmatrix}}.$$

Bu formulalarga Kramer formulalari deyiladi, bunda Δ_1 yordamchi determinant Δ determinantning birinchi ustunini ozod hadlar bilan, Δ_2 da esa ikkinchi ustun ozod hadlar bilan almashtiriladi. Δ determinantga tenglamalar sistemasining determinanti deyiladi.

Shunday qilib, berilgan chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasining determinanti 0 dan farqli bo'lsa, sistema yagona yechimga ega bo'ladi.

Misol. Ushbu

$$\begin{cases} 2x_1 - 3x_2 = 1, \\ 3x_1 + x_2 = 18 \end{cases}$$

tenglamalar sistemasining yechimini toping.

Yechish. Bu sistemaning determinanti

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & -3 \\ 3 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 2 \cdot 1 - (-3) \cdot 3 = 2 + 9 = 11 \neq 0.$$

Demak, berilgan tenglamalar sistemasi yagona yechimga ega.

$$\Delta x_1 = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & -3 \\ 18 & 1 \end{vmatrix} = 1 + 18 \cdot 3 = 55, \quad \Delta x_2 = \begin{vmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 3 & 18 \end{vmatrix} = 36 - 3 = 33.$$

$$\text{Shunday qilib, } x_1 = \frac{\Delta x_1}{\Delta} = \frac{55}{11} = 5, x_2 = \frac{\Delta x_2}{\Delta} = \frac{33}{11} = 3.$$

Matrisaviy usulda yechish.

Ushbu

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1 \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = b_2 \\ \text{K K K K K K K K K K K K} \\ a_{n1}x_1 + a_{n2}x_2 + \dots + a_{nn}x_n = b_n \end{array} \right\} \quad (1)$$

sistemaga n ta nam'alumli tenglamalar sistemasini deyiladi. Sistema

koeffisientlaridan $A = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \Lambda & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \Lambda & a_{2n} \\ \text{-----} \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \Lambda & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix}$, nama'lumlardan $X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \dots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix}$, ozod

hadlardan $B = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \dots \\ b_n \end{pmatrix}$ matritsalar tuzaylik. Bu matritsalar yordamida (1) tenglamalar

sistemani quyidagicha yozish mumkin:

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \Lambda & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \Lambda & a_{2n} \\ \text{-----} \\ a_{m1} & a_{m2} & \Lambda & a_{mn} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ \dots \\ x_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ \dots \\ b_n \end{pmatrix} \text{ yoki } A \cdot X = B \text{ ko'rinishida yozish mumkin.}$$

Agar $\det A \neq 0$ bo'lsa, A^{-1} teskari matritsa mavjud va yagona bo'lishidan $A^{-1} \cdot A \cdot X = A^{-1} \cdot B$ yoki $X = A^{-1} \cdot B$ bo'ladi.

Noma'lumlardan iborat X -ustun matrisani bunday topish matrisaviy usul deyiladi.

Misol. Quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini matritsa usulida yeching.

$$\begin{cases} 2x_1 + 3x_2 + 4x_3 = 1 \\ x_1 + 2x_2 + 3x_3 = 0 \\ 3x_1 + 4x_2 + 6x_3 = 1 \end{cases}$$

Yechish.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 3 & 4 \\ 1 & 2 & 3 \\ 3 & 4 & 6 \end{pmatrix}; \quad B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}; \quad X = \begin{pmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$|A| = 24 + 27 + 16 - 24 - 24 - 1 = 1 \neq 0 \Rightarrow$$

$$A^{-1} = \frac{1}{\Delta} \begin{pmatrix} A_{11} & A_{21} & A_{31} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{32} \\ A_{13} & A_{23} & A_{33} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 & -2 \\ -2 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

$$X = A^{-1} \cdot B = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -2 & 1 \\ 3 & 0 & -2 \\ -2 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad x_1 = 1, x_2 = 1, x_3 = -1$$

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati

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